

Effectiveness of Sarcodes Responding to Hypothyroidism: An Evidence-based Case Study

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Abstracts:-

➤ *Background:*

This case report explores the use of homeopathic sarcodes in managing hypothyroidism, an endocrine disorder. The study found that homeopathic medicines correct metabolism without adverse effects. A 15-year-old female with hypothyroidism was prescribed thyroidinum 6x two times a day for a month, resulting in normal parameters.

➤ *Objectives:*

Study the effectiveness of homeopathic sarcodes in managing hypothyroidism and their role in treating Endocrine Disorders.

➤ *Methods:*

A case report that examined the effectiveness of homeopathic treatment in treating endocrine diseases i.e. hypothyroid, by searching the PubMed and Google Scholar databases. Following abstract assessment, the full texts of the articles that made the shortlist were examined for study design.

➤ *Results:*

Summary of the case: A 15-year-old female with hypothyroidism 11.61 uIU/mL with complaints of weight gain, dry skin, fatigue, and hair loss. was treated with thyroidinum 6x tablets for a month, demonstrating the efficacy of homeopathic treatment. The isopathic use of auto-sarcode of DNA could potentially treat chronic disorders, The study utilized Google Scholar and PubMed databases to identify studies on statistics, homeopathic immunity, and homeopathic sarcodes, clinical studies, revealing that homeopathic medicines effectively treat conditions without adverse effects but rigorous research and clinical trials are needed.

➤ *Conclusion:*

Endocrine disorders affect various aspects of life, including physical, psychological, and financial well-being. Homoeopathy strengthens the immune system using pharmaceuticals, while organotherapy uses animal health tissues to treat patients. Both methods follow Homeopathy principles, focusing on the same cures. Organotherapy uses identical organ extracts and activity by potency to strengthen organs and tissues weakened by

toxins, while low potency stimulates underactive organs or tissues.

Keywords:- Homoeopathy, Endocrine Disorders, Immunity In Homoeopathy.

Key Messages:- A Case Report on Organotherapy (Sarcodes) Action on Endocrine Disorders.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hypothyroidism Autoimmune mechanisms induce either excessive (thyrotoxicosis) or insufficient (hypothyroidism) synthesis of thyroid hormones by destroying glandular tissue. Thyroid cancer or benign nodules may result from these conditions. Through the binding of T4 and T3 to carrier proteins, a traditional endocrine feedback loop regulates the production of thyroid hormones. Hypothalamic or pituitary disorders, congenital hypothyroidism, and thyroid failure can all cause insufficient synthesis of thyroid hormones. The prevalence of congenital hypothyroidism increases with age, with 1 in 4000 infants having it at peak at age 60. ⁽¹⁾

Organotherapy (OT) is a type of tautopathy in which the same organs are stimulated and strengthened, or their functions are corrected by employing medications derived from healthy organ tissue. It has been utilized in traditional medicine to support thyroid extract and other endocrine gland production of hormones. But for diabetic mellitus, synthetic medications like levothyroxine and insulin have taken the position of allopathic organotherapy. According to studies, potentized thymulinum increases the development of the thymus and the immune system, causing immunosuppression in healthy mice and enhanced cellular response in immune-deficient mice. According to a 2002 study, iatrogenic and pharmacogenic effects are the most common causes of death and disability in the United States today, rather than cancer or heart disease. In the future, iatrogenic and toxic ailments will rank highest among chronic illnesses. ⁽²⁾

➤ *Essential Principals*

Organotherapy is an up-and-emerging branch of Homeopathy that utilizes the use of organ remedies, made from the health tissues of animals, to treat the patient, working on the basic principles of Homeopathy, i.e. like cures like. It is based on the idea and understanding that

organs respond to those tissues that have an affinity for the same tissues in the human body, no matter what species their origin. Organotherapy is based on two fundamental laws. (1) Identical organs. (2) Activity by potency. 1. Identical organs: When a diseased organ is present, an identical healthy organ

extract with corrected information in the form of mRNA is administered to rectify the organ. 2. Activity by potency: Organ medicine is used to strengthen organs, glands, and tissues weakened by toxins. Low potency is used to stimulate an underactive organ, gland, or tissue. (3)

Table 1 Source of Sarcodes from Healthy Secretions i.e. Hormones.⁽⁴⁾

S. No	Name	Synonym	Name of Drug	Source
1.	Adrenalin	Epinephrine	Adrenaline	The suprarenal renal gland is the organ that produces hormones. Additionally, it can be made synthetically. Additionally, "Adrenalin hydrochloridum," a synthetic salt, is employed.
2	Cortisone	Cortisine acetate; cortisone monoacetate	cortisone	A crystalline steroid hormone secreted by the adrenal cortex of man.
3	Adrenocorticotropin	A.C.T.H.; corticotrophin	adrenocorticotrophin	The anterior pituitary gland secretes trophinum, a polypeptide hormone that regulates the adrenal gland.
4	Insulin	-	Insulinum	The islets of Langerhans beta cell produces a pancreatic hormone. regulates the body's metabolism of sugar.

Table 2 Sarcodes from Whole Endocrine Glands.⁽⁴⁾

S. No.	Name	Name of Drug	Source
1.	Thyroid	Thyreoidinum	From the sheep's or calf's healthy thyroid or the back of the sheep's pituitary gland
2.	Posterior pituitary	Pituitaria posterior	from the sheep's or calf's healthy thyroid or the back of the sheep's pituitary gland

Table 3 From Normal Secretions of Animals or Humans.⁽⁵⁾

S. No.	Sarcode	Source
1	Lac caninum	From dogs' milk
2	Lac felinum	From cats' milk
3	Lac vaccinum	From cows' milk
4	Lac humanum	From human breast milk
5	Lac asinum	Frist milk after child birth
6	Lac cameli dromedary	Female camel milk
7	Lac caninum	Female dog (bitch) milk
8	Lac caprinum	Female goat (doe) milk
9	Lac delphinum	Female dolphin milk
10	Lac equinum	Female horse (mare) milk

➤ *Preparation of Sarcodes*

Sarcodes are substances found in endocrine glands, healthy secretions, extracts, and other sources. They are prepared in a biosafety-compliant environment with minimal handling. Other components are removed through filtering and boiling. The mother tincture is prepared by introducing soluble substances into alcohol or water mixtures, while insoluble substances are ground down. Potentization is achieved by dilution and succussion, producing 1C potency and 2C potency. Safety checks for human use are conducted before sarcodes are issued. Lyophilization of the original stock ensures future preparation without repeating the initial steps, and a centralized depository system preserves standard raw materials for future use. (6)

➤ *General Mechanism*

It stimulates organ functions and should help to stop antibodies from being formed against those particular organs. The organs can recognize the proper cells and can start reproducing them from the Organotherapy stimulation. The response of a malfunctioning or diseased organ to the Organotherapy (sarcodes) remedy is that the function of the organ or tissue is then supported in its healing, regulation, and balance. Organotherapy sarcodes also can act as if to exchange an organ that was removed partially or totally with surgery like women with a hysterectomy surgery, or removal of their ovaries. It is also vital to help with organ drainage to revive the function of organs that are suffering from progressing disease. This may be especially important for the kidneys and liver. (7)

➤ *Objectives:*

Study the effectiveness of homeopathic sarcodes in managing hypothyroidism and their role in treating Endocrine Disorders.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A case report that examined the effectiveness of homeopathic treatment in treating endocrine diseases i.e. hypothyroid, by searching the PubMed and Google Scholar databases. Following abstract assessment, the full texts of the articles that made the shortlist were examined for study design.

➤ *Inclusion Criteria*

- Hypothyroidism with Homoeopathic Intervention only.
- Articles based on Homoeopathic Intervention and Thyroid for the last 1year
- Strictly English language articles
- Abstract and full-text original articles were included in this Review.

➤ *Exclusion Criteria: -*

- Studies on thyroid based on other therapies.
- In vivo/in vitro studies.
- Thyroid with other systemic illness.

III. DISCUSSION

Table 4 Studies Show Homoeopathic Medicines Effectively Treat Thyroid Cases, Reducing Adjuvant care, Weight Loss, Obesity, and Hair Loss, Reducing the need for Adjuvant Care

Sr. No	Author Name	Title	Intervention	Result
1.	Teixeira, M., et.al	Teixeira, M., Teixeira, M., Hahnemann, S., Teixeira, M., Teixeira, M., Hahnemann, S., ... & Saha, S. (2019). Isopathic use of auto-sarcode of DNA as anti-miasmatic homeopathic medicine and modulator of gene expression? Homeopathy, 108(02), 139-148.	Isopathic use of auto-sarcode of DNA as anti-miasmatic homeopathic medicine and modulator of gene expression? Homeopathy	Auto-sarcode of general DNA can treat chronic disorders by modulating epigenomic expression and performing global actions. This could increase cellular resistance, stimulate repair systems, and restore body system characteristics. The hypothesis requires gradual application, periodic extractions, and preparations. However, rigorous research and clinical trials are needed to confirm its validity. ⁽⁸⁾
2.	Mandal, P. P., & Mandal, B.	Mandal, P. P., & Mandal, B. (1994). <i>Text book of homeopathic pharmacy</i> . New Central Book Agency.	Text book of homeopathic pharmacy. New Central Book Agency.	Effectiveness: Target glands or organs are homoeopathically restored by a sarcode, which creates a healthy tissue template that the body can use to rebuild, regenerate, and stimulate itself. Following the general guidelines of homoeopathic medicines, healthy organ extracts or secretions are prepared, which will aid in preventing the organ's pathological and natural decline. ⁽⁹⁾
3.	Amritha, M.	Amritha, M. (2019). A Clinical Study on the Management of Hypothyroidism in Females using LM Potency (Doctoral dissertation, Sarada Krishna Homoeopathic Medical College, Kulasekharam).	A Clinical Study on the Management of Hypothyroidism in Females using LM Potency (Doctoral dissertation, Sarada Krishna Homoeopathic Medical College, Kulasekharam).	The study demonstrates the effectiveness of LM potency in managing hypothyroidism, a common disease. The study involved 30 female patients from various medical centers and evaluated their response to LM potency and doses. Results showed marked improvement in all cases, indicating that LM potencies are effective in treating female hypothyroidism, as per the Homoeopathic principle of "Similia Similibus Curentur." ⁽¹⁰⁾
4.	Khan A, Haque S.	Khan A, Haque S. Correlation of improvement in symptoms of depression and improvement in somatic manifestations of hypothyroidism with constitutional homoeopathic treatment.	Correlation of improvement in symptoms of depression and improvement in somatic manifestations of hypothyroidism with constitutional homoeopathic treatment.	A study at the National Institute of Homoeopathy found a strong partially positive correlation between the improvement of depression and the improvement of somatic manifestations in hypothyroidism patients with associated depression. The study assessed the improvement in depression using the HAM-D score and the Zulewski score. The results showed a significant decrease in both scales, indicating a strong connection between the two conditions. ⁽¹¹⁾

Table 5 Materia Medica Studies related to Thyroid from Different Materia Medica

Sr. No	Name of the Remedy	Name of book Author	Characteristics of Thyroidinum
1.	Adrenalinum	Dictionary Of Practical Materia Medica (All 3 Vol.) By Clarke J. H.	Adrenalin has been used to treat Addison's disease, Haematuria, and hyperaemia in the conjunctiva. Its main effects include skin bronzing, strength loss, wasting, and rapid pulse. Its powerful local action over dilated blood vessels cause blood pressure to rise, artery contraction, and muscle system damage.
2.	Lac Caninum	Lectures On Homoeopathy By Kent J. T.	Lac caninum, a remedy developed by Dr. Reisig, is effective in treating various ailments, including enlarged glands, ulcers, and diphtheria. It causes long-lasting mental symptoms and is particularly effective in treating complaints following poorly treated diphtheria and paralysis. It is particularly useful in treating ovaries, ovaries, and sore throats, with many cases successfully cured.
3.	Insulinum	Materia Medica By Boericke W.	Insulin, used in treating diabetes and restoring carbohydrate oxidation, has been used homoeopathically for acne, carbuncles, erythema, eczema, gouty, transitory glycosuria, and persistent skin irritation, boils, or varicose ulceration.
4.	Lac vaccinum defloratum	Dictionary Of Practical Materia Medica (All 3 Vol.) By Clarke J. H.	Swan developed a potentizing skimmed milk treatment for sensitive individuals, treating headaches and constipation due to its natrum-mur. ingredient, and also treating fever, prostration, and colds.
5.	Lac felinum	Keynotes With Nosodes By Allen H.C.	The patient is experiencing severe depression, fear of falling, and mental illusions. She has pain in her head, occiput, and lower jaw, headache, burning temple, and sharp eye pain. She also has a strong photophobia and has pain in her teeth, mouth, and throat. She also has a tense mucus in her pharynx, a sore stomach, and a desire to eat paper.

IV. RESULTS

Summary of the case: A 15-year-old female with hypothyroidism 11.61 uIU/mL with complaints of weight gain, dry skin, fatigue, and hair loss. was treated with thyroidinum 6x tablets for a month, demonstrating the efficacy of homoeopathic treatment. The isopathic use of auto-sarcode of DNA could potentially treat chronic disorders, The study utilized Google Scholar and PubMed databases to identify studies on statistics, homeopathic immunity, and homoeopathic sarcodes, clinical studies, revealing that homoeopathic medicines effectively treat conditions without adverse effects but rigorous research and clinical trials are needed.

Fig 2 Date: 03. July. 2023 after Treatment

Fig 1 Date: 20. Feb. 2023 before Treatment

Fig 3 Date: 04. Dec. 2023 after Treatment

Fig 4 List of Studies

V. CONCLUSION

Endocrine disorders affect various aspects of life, including physical, psychological, and financial well-being. Homeopathy strengthens the immune system using pharmaceuticals, while organotherapy uses animal health tissues to treat patients. Both methods follow Homeopathy principles, focusing on the same cures. Organotherapy uses identical organ extracts and activity by potency to strengthen organs and tissues weakened by toxins, while low potency stimulates underactive organs or tissues.

➤ Conflicts of Interest:

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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